

New Synthetic Analogue of Bradykinin

M. A. EL-MAGHRABY

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, University of Assiut, Egypt, A. R. E.

Manuscript received 5 September 1975 ; accepted 1 October 1975

New synthetic analogue of bradykinin containing 4-fluoroproline in positions 2,3 and 7, has been synthesized.

THE chemical structure of the hormones formed by enzymatic breakdown of blood serum proteins "bradykinin and kallidin" which are blood pressure lowering substances, are completely established,¹⁻² and they have been synthesized³⁻⁴. Structure activity relationship of synthetic variation of bradykinin has held an important place in pharmaceutical chemistry, pharmacology, and biochemistry⁶⁻⁹.

For this purpose, new synthetic analogue of bradykinin containing 4-fluoroproline in positions 2, 3 and 7 has been synthesized. Fluoroproline was used because of the unusual and often unexpected properties¹⁰ which the fluorine atom gives to the molecule, also some fluorinated amino acids possess outstanding effectiveness as competitive inhibitors¹¹. Z-L-Pro (4F) ONP¹² was condensed with L-Phe-L-Arg(NO₂)-OH¹⁵ to give the corresponding Z-L-Pro (4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg(NO₂)-OH(I). The benzyloxycarbonyl group of the protected tripeptide was eliminated by using hydrogen bromide in acetic acid¹³, without any effect on the fluorine atom.

The tetra(II), penta(III), hexa IV, hepta V, octa VI and Non VII, peptides were prepared stepwise using the *p*-nitrophenylester method by the following scheme.

The structure of nonpeptide VII was confirmed by its analytical data and by amino acid analysis after its hydrolysis with 6*N* HCl at 110° for about 24 hours. The protected groups used for the protection of the nonpeptide VII was eliminated by catalytic hydrogenation¹⁴ H₂/Pd, and some biological testing are under consideration.

Experimental

The time allowed for the completion of the reaction and the purity of the prepared compounds was controlled by means of thin-layer chromatography (T.L.C.) using freshly prepared solvent (butanol-water-acetic acid 62:26:12). T.L.C. plates were prepared by sluring kiesel gel on microscopic slides (0.25 mm thick) and dried at 120° for ½ hr. Detection of the spots were achieved by putting the plates in a closed tank containing iodine.

N-benzyloxycarbonyl amino acids and peptides were detected by ninhydrin spray on chromatograms after treating with hydrogen bromide in acetic acid at room temperature (20°) for 1 hr. Melting points were determined on Gallen-Kamp melting point apparatus and were uncorrected.

Preparation of Z-L-Pro-(4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg(NO₂)-OH (I): To a solution of Z-L-Pro (4F)-ONP (1.12 g) in ethyl acetate (10 ml); L-Phe-L-Arg (NO₂)-OH¹⁵ (2g) in ethyl acetate (10 ml) was added, and the reaction was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. After the time allowed was consumed, the precipitate was filtered, washed with 2 N HCl, 5% NaHCO₃, ether, and recrystallized from ethyl acetate to give Z-L-Pro (4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg (NO₂)-OH as colourless needle (2.5 g, 80%), m. p. 137-139°, R_f 0.51, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -39^\circ$ (C=1 in D. M. F.), (found C, 56.02; H, 5.40; N, 16.30; F, 3.09, C₂₈H₃₃N₇O₇F. required C, 56.18; H, 5.51; N, 16.39, F, 3.18%).

Preparation of Z-L-Ser-L-Pro (4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg (NO₂)-OH (II): To Z-L-Pro (4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg(NO₂)-OH (0.89) in acetic acid (2.25 ml) was added hydrogen bromide in acetic acid (2 N, 1.8 ml.). After 1 hr. at room temperature dry ether was added. The precipitated hydrobromide was dissolved in the minimum volume of D. M. F., triethylamine (2.6 ml) was added followed by Z-L-Ser (ONP)¹⁵ (0.6 g). After 18 hr. at room temperature the solid mass was mixed with ethyl acetate (75 ml), filtered, washed with 2N HCl, 5% NaHCO₃, ether, and recrystallized from ethyl acetate to give Z-L-Ser-L-Pro (4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg (NO₂)-OH as colourless needle (1.3 g, 83%), m. p. 142-145°, R_f 0.55, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -51^\circ$ (C=1, in D. M. F.), (Found: C, 54.21; H, 5.43; N, 16.29; F, 2.72; C₃₁H₃₃N₈O₉F, required C, 54.30; H, 5.55; N, 16.34; F, 2.77%).

Preparation of Z-L-Phe-L-Ser-L-Pro (4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg (NO₂)-OH. III: To Z-L-Ser-L-Pro (4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg (NO₂)-OH (0.7 g) in acetic acid (2.25 ml) was added hydrogen bromide in acetic acid (2N, 1.8 ml). After 1 hr. at room temperature dry ether was added. The precipitated hydrobromide was filtered, washed with ether and dried over NaOH. The solid mass was dissolved in the minimum amount of D. M. F., triethylamine (2.6 ml) was added followed by Z-L-Phe-ONP (0.4 g)¹⁵. After 18 hour at room temperature, the solid mass was mixed with ethyl acetate (75 ml), filtered, washed with 2NHCl, 5% NaHCO₃, ether, and recrystallized from ethyl acetate to Z-L-Phe-L-Ser-L-Pro (4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg (NO₂)-OH as colourless needle (1.0 g, 90%), m. p. 160-62°, R_f 0.59, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -60^\circ$ C=1, in D.M.F., (found: C, 57.57; H, 5.59; N, 15.01; F, 2.21; C₄₀H₄₇N₉O₁₀F, required C, 57; 67; H, 5.64; N, 15.14; F, 2.28%).

Preparation of Z-Gly-L-Phe-L-Ser-L-Pro (4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg (NO₂)-OH: IV: To Z-L-Phe-L-Ser-L-Pro (4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg (NO₂)-OH (0.72 g) in acetic acid (2.25 ml) was added hydrogen bromide in acetic acid (2N, 1.8 ml). After one hour at room temperature dry ether was added. The precipitated hydrobromide was

filtered, washed with ether and dried over NaOH. The solid mass was dissolved in the minimum amount of D. M. F., triethylamine (2.6 ml) was added followed by Z-Gly-ONP (0.4 g)¹⁵. After 18 hour at room temperature, the solid mass was mixed with ethyl acetate (75 ml), filtered, washed with 2N HCl, 5% NaHCO₃, ether, and recrystallized from ethylacetate to give Z-Gly-L-Phe-L-Ser-L-Pro (4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg (NO₂)-OH. as colourless needle (0.8 g, 88%), m. p. 175-77°, R_f 0.63, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -70^\circ$ C=1, in D. M. F., (found: C, 56.58; H, 5.51; N, 15.69; F, 2.06; C₄₂H₅₀N₁₀O₁₁F, required C, 56.67; H, 5.62; N, 15.74; F, 2.12%).

Preparation of Z-L-Pro-(4F)-L-Gly-L-Phe-L-Ser-L-Pro (4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg (NO₂)-OH(V): To Z-Gly-L-Phe-L-Ser-L-Pro (4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg (NO₂)-OH (0.7 g) in acetic acid (2.25 ml) was added hydrogen bromide in acetic acid (2N, 1.9 ml). After one hour at room temperature dry ether was added. The precipitated hydrobromide was filtered, washed with ether and dried over NaOH. The solid mass was dissolved in the minimum amount of D. M. F., triethylamine (2.6 ml) was added followed by Z-L-Pro-(4F)-ONP¹³ (0.4 g). After 18 hour at room temperature, the solid mass was mixed with ethylacetate (75 ml), filtered, washed with 2N HCl, 5% NaHCO₃, ether and recrystallized from ethylacetate to give Z-L-Pro-(4F)-Gly-L-Phe-Ser-L-Pro (4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg (NO₂)-OH as colourless needle, m. p. 183-85°, R_f 0.65, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -75^\circ$ (C=1, in D. M. F.) (found: C, 56.01; H, 5.51; N, 15.23; F, 3.72, C₄₇H₅₆N₁₁O₁₂F, required C, 56.11; H, 5.57; N, 15.32; F, 3.78%).

Preparation of Z-L-Pro-(4F)-L-Pro-(4F)-L-Gly-L-Phe-L-Ser-L-Pro (4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg (NO₂)-OH(VI): To Z-L-Pro-(4F)-Gly-L-Phe-L-Ser-L-Pro (4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg(NO₂)-OH (0.9 g) in acetic acid (2.25 ml) was added hydrogen bromide in acetic acid (2N, 1.8 ml). After 1 hr. at room temperature dry ether was added. The precipitated hydrobromide was filtered, washed with ether, and dried over NaOH. The solid mass was dissolved in the minimum amount of D. M. F., triethylamine (2.6 ml) was added followed by Z-L-Pro (4F)-ONP¹² (0.4 g). After 18 hr. at room temperature, the solid mass was mixed with ethylacetate (75 ml), filtered, washed with 2N HCl, 5% NaHCO₃, ether, and recrystallized from ethylacetate to give Z-L-Pro (4F)-L-Pro-(4F)-Gly-L-Phe-L-Ser-L-Pro (4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg (NO₂)-OH. as colourless needle (1.1 g, 90%), m. p. 196-97°, R_f 0.70 $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -77^\circ$ C=1, in D. M. F., (found C, 55.59; H, 5.48; N, 14.93; F, 4.99, C₅₂H₆₂N₁₂O₁₃F₃, required C, 55.71; H, 5.53; N, 15.00; F, 5.08%).

Preparation of Z-L-Arg (NO₂)-L-Pro (4F)-L-Pro (4F)-Gly-L-Phe-L-Ser-L-Pro(4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg (NO₂)-OH: To Z-L-Pro-(4F)-L-Pro-(4F)-Gly-L-Phe-L-Ser-L-Pro (4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg (NO₂)-OH (0.7 g) in acetic acid (2.25 ml) was added hydrogen bromide in acetic acid (2N, 1.8 ml). After 1 hr. at room temperature dry ether was added. The precipitated hydrobromide was filtered, washed with ether, and dried over NaOH. The solid mass was dissolved in the minimum amount of D. M. F., triethylamine (2.6 ml) was added followed by

Z. L-Arg (NO₂)-ONP¹⁵ (0.35 g). After 18 hr. at room temperature the solid mass was mixed with ethylacetate (75 ml), filtered, washed with 2N HCl, 51. NaHCO₃, ether, and recrystallized from ethylacetate to give Z-L-Arg (NO₂)-L-Pro (4F)-Pro-4F)-Gly-L-Phe-L-Ser-L-Pro (4F)-L-Phe-L-Arg (NO₂)-OH. as colourless needle (0.79 g, 90%), m.p. 202-3°, R_f 0.75, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -79$ (C=1 in D. M. F.), (Found : C, 52.57 ; H, 5.41 ; N, 17.91 ; F, 4.28 ; C₅₈H₇₃N₁₇O₁₄F₃, required C, 52.68 ; H, 5.52 ; N, 18.00 ; F, 4.31%). Amino acid analysis : Arginine 1.96 (2 mol) ; fluoroproline 3.01 (3 mol) ; phenylalanine 2.00 (2 mol), serine 1.00 (1 mol), and glycine 0.99 (1 mol).

References

1. R. A. BOISSONNAS, S. GUTTMANN and P. A. JAQUENOUD, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1960, **43**, 1481.
2. S. GUTTMANN and R. A. BOISSONNAS, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1961, **44**, 1713.
3. S. GUTTMANN, J. PLEES and R. A. BOISSONNAS, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1962, **45**, 170.
4. E. D. NICOLAIDES and H. A. DE WALD, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 3872.
5. I. Z. SIEMION, *Roczniki Chem.*, 1964, **38**, 133.
6. M. BODANSZKY, J. T. SHEEHAN, M. A. ONDETTI and S. LANDE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 991.
7. H. A. DE WALD, D. C. BEHN, M. S. MORGAN, A. G. RENFREW and A. M. MOORE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 4367.
8. E. D. NICOLAIDES, H. A. DE WALD and M. K. CRAFT, *Med. Chem.*, 1963, **6**, 739.
9. E. SCHRODER, *Ann. Chem. Liebigs*, 1964, **673**, 168.
10. W. BERSTOCK and C. MIDLRED, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4800.
11. M. K. MITCHELL and C. KEIMANN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 1232.
12. M. A. EL-MAGHRABY, *J. Chem.*, (U. A. R.) 1974, **17**, No. I
13. M. BERGMANN and L. ZERVES, *Ber. Dent. Chem. Ges.*, 1932, **65**, 1192.
14. K. B. SEOPES and G. T. YOUNG, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 782.
15. M. BODANSZKY, *Nature*, 1955, **175**, 685 ; *Acta. Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1957, **10**, 335.